

XVI.

ANEURISM OF THYROID ARTERY.

GEORGE F. COTT, M.D.

CLINICAL PROFESSOR OF OTOLOGY, MEDICAL DEPARTMENT UNIVERSITY OF BUFFALO.

Man, aged 62, height about 5 feet 5 inches, weight very little over 100.pounds, estimated. Called to see him about 2:30 one morning because of difficult breathing. His symptoms seemed to point to asthma, but after close examination the diagnosis was left in doubt. While inquiring into his history I was informed that he had already had twenty-

three doctors since the symptoms first manifested themselves several years ago. The patient was always cheerful during the attacks. He had not the asthmatic hoarseness nor the peculiar characteristic rales so pronounced in asthma. Nearly all of his previous physicians pronounced the condition one of asthma, as did also the gentlemen I met in consultation. I did not agree with this opinion, but could not explain what caused the symptoms. Close inquiry did not elicit any facts which might lead on to causation. Drugs seemed of no particular use since so many had been tried and had failed so I treated the patient topically when he came to the office, not expecting any result. The throat and

larynx and part of the trachea could easily be examined but nothing unusual detected. This condition kept on for several months, when his symptoms became markedly worse. Being satisfied that spasmodic asthma was not the cause of the distressed breathing, I proposed tracheotomy as possibly affording some relief. To this the patient consented and the trachea was opened under cocain anesthesia. This procedure gave him considerable relief, but he gradually grew weaker and died three days later. At the post-mortem we found some thickening in bronchial tubes due to chronic bronchitis. A large mass of clotted blood the size of a man's hand and which looked like liver, was found along the trachea, also a tumor one and a half inches in diameter, apparently attached to the trachea and ready to penetrate by erosion. It had already destroyed the soft tissues between the tracheal rings. This was examined microscopically by Dr. Bentz of the Laboratory at the University of Buffalo and found to be clotted blood. The tumor, situated within the tracheal wall by pressure upon the pneumo-gastric, caused the difficult breathing, simulating spasmodic asthma. The relief after tracheotomy was no doubt due to the bursting of the tumor thereby relieving pressure on the pneumo-gastric.

Post-mortem diagnosis: Aneurism of thyroid artery.